

ANALYTICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES ON DELAMINATION ARREST FEATURES IN AIRCRAFT COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

For large integrated composite structures, delamination is the critical damage type as there exists no natural arrest mechanism. Subsequently, one common solution to minimize the danger is to install fasteners, clamping the laminate together and partially arresting the delamination prior to significant growth. Research has indicated that fasteners help limit the growth of delaminations, with more fasteners installed in series providing increasing benefit. These arrest features slow and redirect the propagation of the crack, first by compressing the lamina together and second by transferring load via shear engagement of the fastener. In conjunction, work has found that fastener spacing can be increased beyond the typical spacing of 5 fastener diameters; experimental and computational studies have indicated that the failure mode can be shifted away from delamination under both static and fatigue loading even with a significantly greater fastener spacing. However, research has also shown that arresting fatigue delaminations is a greater challenge.

Nomenclature

D	=Fastener Diameter
$\frac{da}{dN}$	=Crack growth per cycle
ΔG	= Range of G for one fatigue cycle $\Delta G = G_{max} - G_{min}$
G	= Total Strain Energy Release Rate
G_C	= Critical Total Strain Energy Release Rate
G_I	= Mode I Strain Energy Release Rate
G_{II}	= Mode II Strain Energy Release Rate
G_{IC}	= Critical Mode I Strain Energy Release Rate
G_{IIC}	= Critical Mode II Strain Energy Release Rate
G_{max}	= Maximum value of G for a fatigue cycle
G_{min}	= Minimum value of G for a fatigue cycle

I. Introduction

In order to reduce weight and improve performance, carbon/epoxy composites are increasingly utilized in primary aircraft structures. This change in material has then shifted the critical damage type from fatigue cracking, commonly found in metallic structures, to delamination, found in laminated carbon/epoxy structures. Because delaminations are typically created by unpredictable discrete events, unlike the measurable cyclic loading which drives fatigue cracking, traditional damage tolerant design techniques are not applicable. As a result, fasteners are employed in current composite aircraft structures, often in a dual use role, for load transfer and addressing this type of damage. The fasteners are assumed

to arrest the cracks as they reach the fastener, providing safety by limiting the extent of the damage. Previous research by Cheung [1] has shown the limited ability of an isolated fastener to arrest the crack, but further work indicates that the addition of a second fastener installed in series, when properly installed in a toughened composite system, effectively suppresses the crack.[2] However, simply installing fastener arrays without optimizing the configuration leads to significant weight penalties, due to the fasteners as well as the need for more structure to endure the stress concentration created by the fastener holes.

Building on the previous studies which have yielded critical understandings of the mechanisms of the arrest feature, the installation of multiple fasteners in series to enhance the crack arrest effectiveness under both static and fatigue loading are being studied. Experimental work is being employed to guide the modeling techniques to ensure all critical parameters are captured. This experimental work indicated a drop in arrest effectiveness when larger tolerances are utilized. The system still shifts the damage mode away from delamination, with tensile failure being the ultimate failure mode, however greater crack extension occurs. This further confirms that two fasteners installed in series provide a dramatic improvement in crack arrest over an isolated fastener and suggest that the clearance of the hole is a critical parameter. Good agreement is observed between the analytical and experimental studies, with ongoing research continuing to extend the understanding of this critical structural feature. [3]

II. Analytical Studies A. Modeling

The finite element analysis represents two carbon/epoxy split beams joined together by two 0.25 inch titanium fasteners installed in series, shown in Figure 1. This represents a simplified skin-stringer delamination arrest scenario. The primary analysis is conducted in two dimension, as this provides a good compromise between rapidity of results and accuracy. Each plate is 10 inches long; sensitivity studies found this length sufficient to avoid boundary condition effects, any longer would simply add excess complexity to the analysis. The thickness of each plate was set at 0.18 inches thick which is the nominal thickness of the experimental samples. The primary material system being utilized was T800/3900-2 with the material properties summarized in Table 1.

	English Units	SI Units
Ply thickness	0.0075 in	0.1905 mm
E_1	20.6×10^6 psi	142.0 GPa
$E_2 = E_3$	1.13×10^6 psi	7.79 GPa
$G_{12} = G_{13}$	0.58×10^6 psi	3.99 GPa
G_{23}	0.52×10^6 psi	3.6 GPa
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$		0.34
ν_{23}		0.40
G_{IC}	1.6 in-lb./in ²	280.2 J/m ²
G_{IIC}	14.0 in-lb./in ²	2452 J/m ²
η		1.75

Table 1. Composite laminar material properties (T800/3900-2) [4]

Modeling of the material properties was accomplished in multiple ways. The initial model which was derived from the successful modeling technique of previous models by Bruun, Cheung and Lin [13] modeled each individual ply through the thickness individually. This required 48 elements through the thickness and to have a well-conditioned model, had 200,000 degrees of freedom, increasing the solution time. However, modeling showed that the problem was largely extensional, the individual plies did not need to be modeled, and instead a simplified model could be utilized. This model reduced the number of elements through the thickness to 16, the minimum number possible to model a quasi-isotropic symmetric repeated laminate. As a result, the model complexity was reduced to less than 40,000 degrees of freedom, drastically speeding the simulation due to the cumulative reduction in time for each iteration in the VCCT analysis.

2-D 4-node quadrilateral plane strain elements, CPE4R, are utilized to model the plates in Abaqus. The element properties are assigned layer by layer representing the lamina properties. For the simplified case, this resulted in a layup of $(0/45/90/-45)_s$ where each ply was three times the nominal ply thickness. Meanwhile, to capture the fastener's influence, two springs are employed at each fastener to represent the shear and tensile stiffness, determined from the fastener flexibility equations proposed by Huth[5] for the shear stiffness and the assumption that the fastener acts as a constant diameter bar under tensile loading. In order to propagate the crack, virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) and the BK law is used to determine the mixed-mode crack propagation behavior.[6]

Figure 1. The Two-beam Model for ABAQUS modeling

Further simplification of the modeling was done to create a 1 dimensional model. This model represents the system as an assemblage of uniaxial bars and springs. Currently, the design does not capture the effects of bending, however for the current experimental work, because the primary driver of crack growth is extension, it is not an issue. This model is excellent for fatigue analysis as it has less than 10 degrees of freedom, providing rapid results.

As research has indicated that the delaminations propagate along the stiffest interface, which is a 0/0 interface for the work presented here, the assumption that the crack remained along the centerline is appropriate [7]. As a result, the delamination is assumed to propagate in a self-similar fashion; the crack tip remains at the prescribed interface between the two beams, regardless of load conditions. In addition, to model fastener preload, a non-linear spring is utilized which enforces a non-zero spring force at zero spring displacement. Similarly, to capture the delay in engagement due to clearance, the model has a spring with zero stiffness over a displacement equal to the assumed hole clearance. To propagate the crack, the simulation begins with the nodes tied together, and once the load satisfies the energy release rates required for crack propagation, the crack tip node constraint is then released, with the next node along the interface becoming the new crack tip [8].

To evaluate the fatigue performance of the system, the Paris law is employed. In Abaqus, this is the direct cyclic option. In both cases, the cyclic loading spectrum produces a ΔG which allows for extrapolation of the damage progression. Because the delaminations are dominated by the matrix properties, fatigue evaluation techniques similar to those developed for metals can be utilized, including composite material da/dN vs. ΔG curves.

A second model was also developed utilizing the same methodology to evaluate the ability to scale the system for varying laminate thicknesses and fastener sizes. This model represented a similar quasi-isotropic layup one third the thickness of the prior case. Similarly the fasteners were scaled from $\frac{1}{4}$ inch to 0.0866 inches, the diameter of a 2-56 bolt and approximately $\frac{1}{3}$ of 0.25 inches. Otherwise the quasi-static and fatigue modeling techniques utilized were identical.

Finally, analytical models which represented unfastened fatigue specimen design were created. The first model was based on the ENF test specimen described in ASTM D7905, and second model shown below utilized three plates, each with the layup $(0/45/90/-45)_s$. This model was derived from work done by Gray [7] and allowed for the modeling of fatigue under pure Mode II while under tensile loading compared to the ENF testing which utilized bending. The primary benefit of this is the higher frequencies achievable with the design shown in figure 2 due to lower machine extension required to meet the same ΔG compared to a flexure specimen.

Figure 2: Three Plate Fatigue Property Specimen

B. Modeling Results

The first fastener effectively shuts down Mode I propagation under all fastener configurations and Mode II becomes the dominant mode, seen in figure 4 and propagation continues as shown in figure 3. Of note in all of the figures depicting experimental results, for clarity only one average result is shown which represents the average response of 3 or more replicate specimens which fell within 10%. Additionally, the failure of the composite is not modeled, additional analysis could determine this cutoff value. As expected, changing the fracture toughness of the laminate shifts the curve vertically, a lower value will result in lower propagation loads. Additionally, it can be seen that clearance changes the propagation curve significantly, suggesting that this is a critical parameter to control.

While the first fastener suppresses Mode I propagation by suppressing the opening mode, it is ineffective in fully arresting the crack; the crack continues in Mode II. Clearance delays the engagement of the fastener in shear, meaning that clearance typical of manufactured assemblies (0.007 in for 0.25 in hole) significantly reduces the arrest effectiveness of the system as seen in figure 3. The fasteners resist the Mode II propagation by providing load alleviation at the crack tip through the engagement of the fastener in shear, clearance delays this, and thus delays the effectiveness of the fastener. Load transfer will also occur via crack face friction generated from the clamping of the fasteners. While the frictional transfer aids the arrest of crack propagation, particularly as the preload is increased, current research has shown that the effect is typically dwarfed by the fastener load transfer in quasi-static testing.

Additionally, the upper curve in figure 3 can be seen to have a continuously positive slope while the lower curves have a zero slope along some intervals. A zero slope indicates unstable crack growth. This loss in stability is exacerbated by a reduction in fracture toughness, visualized by the lower load required to grow the crack.

Figure 3. Propagation Load vs. Crack-Tip Location

Figure 4. ERR Components vs. Crack-Tip Location and Experimental Overlay

Additionally, seen in figure 5, modeling suggests that clearance is a critical factor when evaluating the fatigue life. Under cyclic loading, a zero clearance system effectively arrests the crack under subcritical loading, however with the inclusion of minimal clearance, the delamination propagates, and with a typical clearance value (0.007 in), the effect is worsened.

The underlying cause for this effect is the dramatic change in cyclic stresses at the crack tip when the fastener clearance is included. The relative displacement of the two plates in the system is very small, thus the increase in clearance dramatically increases the value of ΔG by reducing the amount of load alleviation at the crack tip.

As a result, while clearly greater clearance provides a more detrimental effect, even a minor value of clearance results in a significant loss in fatigue life. Furthermore, none of the current models incorporate hole damage accumulation, however, as seen in figure 6, hole damage has been observed in certain specimens which have experienced higher cyclic stresses and when this phenomenon occurs, current research suggests a decrement in fatigue life should be expected as the hole is softened and load transfer reduced.

Figure 5: Fatigue Performance of Varying Clearance

Figure 6: Hole Damage on fatigue test specimen

III. Experimental Validation A. Experimental Specimen Specifications

A novel delamination arrest experiment has been created to validate the analytical tools. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the specimen design and figure 7 shows the experimental specimen, which has been retained from previous research. Carbon/epoxy pre-preg tape with a quasi-isotropic layup, $((0/45/90/-45)_{3S}/\text{Crack})_S$, or 50% zero layup $((0/45/0/-45/0/90)_{2S}/\text{Crack})_S$ were tested. The initial crack is implanted via an FEP insert at the mid-plane of the specimen. The holes were drilled using carbide drills of either 0.2500 (zero clearance) or 0.2570 (clearance) diameter. Two titanium fasteners, 0.25 inches in diameter are used and tightened to a prescribed torque, typically 40 in-lb. The specimen width was chosen as 5D or 1.25 inches. [2]

Figure 7. Two-Plate Crack Arrest Specimen

The specimens were tested in tension with the crack tip tracked visually. The specimen was painted white to enhance the crack tip visibility and a 0.1 inch scale was marked on the side. Additional techniques were explored to provide automated crack trip tracking however none proved to be as robust as manual tracking. As a result, visual tracking was retained, for fatigue loading, the test was paused when the displacement required to achieve the load spectrum was found to have changed to a significant degree, indicating a loss in specimen stiffness and crack propagation.

Fatigue specimens consist of the same described specimen configuration, however these experience cyclic loading. The peak loading approximates the expected cyclic load for the specimen configuration, approaching the initial crack propagation load at 8,000 lb. for the described configuration with an amplitude of 3,800 lbs. The loading spectrum consisted of constant amplitude loading to validate the predictive techniques, further research is expected to utilize spectrum loading to expand the capability of the analytical methods.

As well, ENF specimens based on ASTM D7905 were created to evaluate the unfastened fatigue performance of the material system in question. Additional specimens of a novel three plate configuration derived from work by Gray [7] which were theorized to provide more rapid results due to a lower displacement necessary to create the equivalent strain energy release rate at the crack tip providing higher cyclic frequency during testing while still utilizing a quasi-isotropic layup for consistency. The data was then utilized in the modeling to ultimately predict the performance of bolted/bonded structures based on the unfastened fatigue properties.

A final set of experimental samples was created to validate the modeling methodology as the problem scales in size. This mimicked the scaled down analytical model, consisting of $1/3^{\text{rd}}$ thickness samples with

a quasi-isotropic layup and steel 2-56 bolts which are 0.0866 inches in diameter. Clearance was determined by the wire drill sizes; interference fit and 0.003 inches.

B. Experimental Results

As seen in figure 8, the successful tests showed a consistent stabilization of the crack propagation and superior arrest compared to a single fastener. Based on previous research by C.H. Cheung et al [2], it is expected that the crack curved around the fastener, supported by C-scans as shown in Figure 9. As such, the experimental results, tracking the crack tip on the edge of the specimen indicate the crack has traveled further past the fastener compared to the model which tracks the crack tip at the centerline. Additionally it can be noted that the instability of laminates with a low fracture toughness is not captured by the finite element modeling. This is currently being investigated to ensure broad applicability of the modeling techniques, but good engineering design would avoid a laminate with low fracture toughness in parts where delaminations are expected.

Figure 8. Experimental vs. Finite Element Results

Figure 9: Delaminated specimens (yellow is still bonded, blue is delaminated)

Further testing was conducted on another typical laminate configurations, 50% 0 which verified the general applicability of the modeling methodology. It was found that stiffer laminates benefit less from the installation of fasteners because the crack propagates at a lower overall strain. This means that the fastener, acting like a spring, provides less load alleviation compared to softer laminates such as quasi-isotropic because the displacements are lower. However, the fastener was still beneficial, particularly in

forcing the crack to propagate in mode II, and did provide some load alleviation as slope of the curve was positive. Interestingly, for asymmetric laminates, such as where one plate is 50% 0, the other quasi-isotropic, the crack propagation is sensitive to where the load is applied. Greater crack propagation was observed when the softer laminate is the loaded laminate. This discrepancy in stiffness creates a greater strain energy release rate for an equivalent loading, lowering the crack arrest effectiveness by reducing the differential displacement of the two parts which leads to fastener load transfer. This result can be extended to off centerline cracks. Depending on the location through the thickness of the laminate, the crack arrest effectiveness can be changed. Typically the larger unloaded section is relative to the unloaded section, the lower the crack arrest effectiveness. However in typical structures in service it is expected that cases such as this would not occur as fiber breakage would be extensive, compromising the tensile integrity of the structure and requiring repair before the delamination arrest capability was dramatically affected.

Fatigue testing was done to derive the da/dN curve for the material, which was then utilized in the predictions to enhance the accuracy over the generic material properties derived from literature. [8] However, as seen in figure 5, the fatigue predictions tended to be under-conservative, predicting a greater fatigue life than what was tested. Investigations are ongoing to determine if a consistent scale factor can be utilized to relate the two different fatigue performances.

In addition, seen below, the predictions performed reasonably for the derivative model after significant revision. The underlying cause for the initial significant discrepancies appear to be the sensitivity of the model to variations in fastener flexibility. The spring stiffness of the fastener provides load alleviation at the crack tip and as the system becomes smaller, errors in the fastener flexibility become magnified. As a result, careful modeling or experimental verification, as was done here, is necessary to determine the fastener flexibility.

Figure 10. Scaled version experimental and analytical fatigue predictions

IV. Discussion

As seen in figures 5 and 10, the experimental and analytical responses are similar. The static testing and analysis have better correlation which is to be expected considering the original research was conceived to model the quasi-behavior and has only recently been extended to incorporate fatigue. Additionally, the correlation between the scaled down version is reasonably good, indicating that the methodology can be scaled to varying laminate sizes provided careful preliminary analysis is performed.

The inclusion of clearance in the tested samples and finite element solutions indicates the need to control the clearance tightly as increasing values can be seen to lower crack resistance and can cause a loss in stability, exacerbated by a low toughness.[4] Overall, the finite element model captures the delamination arrest behavior of the system for two different materials, as seen above with the two different curves.

Fatigue testing has also shown that the use of the direct cyclic approach in Abaqus, which uses the virtual crack closure technique to extract the strain energy release rates and the Paris Law to extrapolate the crack growth for subcritical loading to be a viable approach. In the testing of the identical 48 ply specimens, the predicted and experimental results matched reasonably well. However it can be noted that the finite element solutions tend to over predict the fatigue life; this is assumed to be due to discrepancies in da/dN data because changing this parameter allows the curves to be shifted and better agreement to be obtained. Further testing and analysis should improve agreement either through improved curves or consistent scale factors.

Meanwhile, the fatigue of the smaller system was also reasonably well but required more work to reach the same level of accuracy. Unsurprisingly the analysis results look similar to those of the larger model, this is to be expected as the model was simply reduced in size. Meanwhile, the fastener flexibility and modeling techniques causing the fastener in the model initially to be more effective than in reality, as a result, careful 3D finite element modeling or testing is required to establish the fastener flexibility. Admittedly, the thinness of these specimens is outside the typical range for which Huth's fastener flexibility in carbon composites was designed for.

Meanwhile, the testing methods can also be improved. In particular, the current testing was only in tension-tension due to the limitations of the test equipment. Compression capable grips were not able to be acquired in time to perform testing, however it is expected that tension-compression loading will cause greater crack propagation compared to tension-tension loading. An additional challenge in compressive loading is preventing a thin bar such as the test specimen from buckling. In this case the buckling load is approximately 2,000 lbs. This could be increased by shortening the specimen, however this limits the amount of crack propagation which can occur before the grips begin to influence the result. As a result, anti-buckling fixtures could be employed. As well, the effects of buckling could be included in the analysis, buckling will create a bending stress which is expected to increase the strain energy release rate for a given load, reducing the fatigue life of the specimen. As well, sub laminate buckling could increase the crack propagation if mode I is able to reemerge.

V. Conclusion

The effective arrest capability and limitations of multiple fasteners installed in series has been demonstrated. Based on a two plate design, similar to common primary composite aircraft structures, the specimen initially generates a mixed mode propagation state which then demonstrates the ability of the fastener to eliminate mode I propagation. Variations in laminate layup and thickness have shown that the model retains reasonable predictive accuracy with room for improvement when the configuration varies significantly, particularly in fatigue.

For both static and fatigue loading, finite element modeling techniques have been developed to accurately predict the delamination response. The models compare well with one another and the experimental results, with the best agreement occurring when comparing the model and experiments which have been studied in the greatest detail. The clamping effect of the fasteners has been shown to eliminate mode I propagation for a significant linear distance, allowing for an increased spacing of the fasteners in a crack arrest configuration compared to that which is typical for load transfer. Meanwhile, the analysis has indicated that the fastener joint stiffness is the primary force resisting propagation, with friction providing a noticeable benefit.

Static testing has shown that clearance is a key parameter in arresting cracks, particularly in conjunction with laminates with a low fracture toughness. Zero clearance holes allowed the fasteners to arrest the crack prior at the second fastener with the sample failing in net section failure. Meanwhile, for a laminate with an average to high fracture toughness, the inclusion of clearance resulted in propagation a significant distance past the second fastener but still ultimately lead to arrest, but for a laminate with a low fracture toughness, the crack propagated unstably through the entire length of the specimen.

Furthermore, in fatigue loading, the influence of clearance became even more dramatic. A sample where the fastener fit tightly in the hole was able to effectively arrest the crack between the two fasteners while the inclusion of clearance resulted in significant crack propagation through the length of the sample. This trend was also reflected in the scaled down samples. As such, research indicates that for delamination arrest under fatigue loading clearance is a critical parameter to control.

The results of this research contribute to the understanding of fasteners as a crack arrest feature in composite aircraft structures. Understanding the arrest capability and limitations of fasteners installed explicitly for arrest, as well as bolts whose secondary feature is providing delamination arrest, will allow for the optimization of fastener features to minimize the fastener weight penalty while maintaining safety by limiting the size of the disbond/delamination, sustaining the component's structural integrity and possibly extending its certified lifespan.

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